

Access to non-published data in PATHWAYS- Metadata summary

The PATHWAYS project seeks to enhance sustainable practices throughout the supply and production chains of the European livestock sector. Its primary goal is to minimize environmental impacts while meeting societal demands for safe, nutritious, and affordable meat and dairy products. To achieve this, the project team will undertake various actions organized into 10 work packages:

WP1: Multi-actor engagement for system redesign

WP2: Development and consolidation of scenario assessments for holistic solutions and pathways

WP3: New measurements and modeling for welfare, biodiversity, emissions, and farm practices

WP4: Assessing consumer behavior, current and future diets

WP5: Farm-to-fork holistic Life Cycle Assessment

WP6: Assessment of the circular economy and territorial ecosystem services

WP7: Assessment of supply chain dynamics and market power

WP8: Knowledge exchange, dissemination, and transfer of outcomes

WP9: Coordination and management

WP10: Ethics requirements

Data Description

The data collection process is closely aligned with the project's objectives and includes the following:

Farm-level Data Collection (WPs 1 and 3): Up to 15 farmers from each of the 16 practice hubs (totaling 240) and 50 individual stakeholders from the European multi-actor platform will provide insights on sustainability and feedback on project outcomes during face-to-face workshops. Additionally, technical and economic data will be gathered from 3 to 20 farms in each practice hub (around 150 farms) using a standardized protocol, which is a modified version of the Public Goods tool (Gerrard et al., 2012).

Consumer and Value Chain Data Collection (WPs 4 and 7): Data will be gathered from 400-600 consumers in WP4 and approximately 1200 stakeholders in WP7. This will be supplemented by data derived from various interviews and workshops across WPs 1-8.

For comprehensive details about PATHWAYS data—including its origin, types, formats, expected size, and utility—please refer to the table below. To request access to non-published data described in the table, please contact the PATHWAYS management team via the project website: <https://pathways-project.com/>

Table 1 : Summary of data per work package (*= Data available via instructions given in Metadata file on Zenodo ** = Data directly available via publication record on Zenodo, *** = Data to be made available in Zendo via publication / Deliverable currently in progress)

	Task	Activity	Type of data	Subject	Newly generated/ already existing data	Data format (Excel, Word, text file)	Nature of data (numerical, oral, visual)	Data type (observational, experimental, simulated/ modelled, derived from databases)	Data volume (if known 1 - 500 MB = small, 501 MB - 5 GB = medium, over 5 GB = large)	Methodology of data collection	Personal/ sensitive data? Yes/No	Will data be published? Yes/No	Metadata file done? Yes/No
WP1	1.1	Establish database of stakeholders	Contact details of stakeholders	Humans	New	Word file	Text	Database	<1MB	Online form	Y	N	Y*
	1.2	Sustainability assessment	Farm practice data	Technical data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Excel sheets (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	1.3	Workshops	Personal details of practice hub members and their feedback	Humans	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Online form	Y	N	Y*
	1.3	Living labs	Data collected from animal/ farm /value chain assessments	Animals, humans, technical data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Experimental	<1GB	Excel sheets (offline)	N	N	Y*
	1.4	Workshops	Personal details of MA Platform members and their feedback	Humans	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<10MB	Online form	Y	N	Y*

WP2	2.1	Literature review; interviews	Data from past projects, and scientific and technical literature	Humans / lit review	Already existing	Word file	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y**
	Task	Activity	Type of data	Subject	Newly generated/ already existing data	Data format (Excel, Word, text file)	Nature of data (numerical, oral, visual)	Data type (observational, experimental, simulated/modelled, derived from databases)	Data volume (if known 1 - 500 MB = small, 501 MB - 5 GB = medium, over 5 GB = large)	Methodology of data collection	Personal/ sensitive data? Yes/No	Will data be published? Yes/No	Metadata file done? Yes/No
WP2	2.3	Macroeconomic modelling	Economic data from published databases, scientific and technical literature	Modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	N*
	2.4	Review of project results and focus groups	Responses from stakeholders, sustainability assessment data from elsewhere in the project	Human and technical data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	Y	Y	N*
WP3	3.1	Establish database of farm business data	Farm business data	Financial data	Already existing	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Excel sheets (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	3.2	Review of project results and focus groups, farm level animal welfare data	Data from past projects, and scientific and technical literature, farm practice data, animal welfare data	Humans, animals	Already existing	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y***
	3.3	Review of project results and focus groups, farm level biodiversity data	Data from past projects, and scientific and technical literature, farm practice data, biodiversity data	Humans, grassland	Already existing	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	N	Y*
	3.4	Review of published data	GHG estimation methodologies	Technical data	Already existing	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y*

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WP3	3.5	Indicator evaluation	Data from scientific publications and that collected as part of T2.1	Technical data	Already existing	Word, files, published literature, text files, excel files	Text	Database	<30 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y*
WP4	4.1	Web-based public opinion survey (Italy, France, Germany, Romania)	Consumer willingness to pay, dietary, sex and gender, mindsets and socio-demographic characteristics data	Humans	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Experimental	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	Y	Y	Y***
	4.2	Database collation / assessment	Inventory of (micro)nutrients required / supplied. Use of data generated by T4.1 to generate "consumer archetypes"	Food	Already existing	Word, files, published literature, text files, excel files	Text	Database	<3 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y***
	4.3	Focus groups	Consumer attitudes	Humans	New	Word, files, published literature, text files, excel files	Text	Database	<3 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	Y	Y	N
WP5	5.1	Literature review; Delphi consultation	Assessment methods for improving LCA	Human and technical data	New	Word, files, published literature, text files, excel files	Text	Database	<30 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y**

	5.2	Modelling of environmental impact resulting from farm practices	Environmental impact resulting from farm practices	Modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y*
	Task	Activity	Type of data	Subject	Newly generated/ already existing data	Data format (Excel, Word, text file)	Nature of data (numerical, oral, visual)	Data type (observational, experimental, simulated/ modelled, derived from databases)	Data volume (if known 1 - 500 MB = small, 501 MB - 5 GB = medium, over 5 GB = large)	Methodology of data collection	Personal/ sensitive data? Yes/No	Will data be published? Yes/No	Metadata file done? Yes/No
WP5	5.3	Modelling of environmental impact resulting from farm practices	Environmental impact of innovative farm practices in the Phubs	Modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	N
	5.4	Assessment of current and future value chains	Modelling of impacts of future scenarios, Environmental impact of future scenarios	Technical and modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	N
WP6	6.1	Stakeholder consultation via questionnaires and focus groups	Ranking of ecosystem services by stakeholder groups	Humans	New	Word, files, published literature, text files, excel files	Text	Experimental	<30 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	Y	Y	Y*
	6.2	Modelling of circular economy at different spatial levels	Impact of current livestock systems on circular economy	Modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y*
	6.3	Modelling of ecosystem processes and their impacts at scale	Environmental data	Modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	N

	6.4	Assessment of ecosystem service impacts under range of scenarios	Environmental a under future scenarios	Modelling data	New	Excel files, Word files	Numerical, text	Database	<1GB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	N
	Task	Activity	Type of data	Subject	Newly generated/ already existing data	Data format (Excel, Word, text file)	Nature of data (numerical, oral, visual)	Data type (observational, experimental, simulated/modelled, derived from databases)	Data volume (if known 1 - 500 MB = small, 501 MB - 5 GB = medium, over 5 GB = large)	Methodology of data collection	Personal/ sensitive data? Yes/No	Will data be published? Yes/No	Metadata file done? Yes/No
WP7	7.1	Value chain mapping	Data from past projects, and scientific and technical literature. Responses from stakeholders	Humans / literature review	New	Word, files, published literature, text files	Text	Database	<30 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	N	Y	Y*
	7.2	Development of scoring method for value chain sustainability assessment	List of metrics and expert feedback	Human and technical data	New	Word, files, published literature, text files	Text, numerical	Database	<30 MB	Word documents and Excel sheets (offline)	Y	Y	N
	7.3	Identification of "levers" for change	List of levers / characteristics for future value chains	Humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10 MB	Word documents (offline)	N	Y	N
WP8	8.1	Development of knowledge exchange strategy for the project	Using data/material generated by project activities to communicate to stakeholders using human data (Name, email, country, company, occupation) when consented	Project data and humans		Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	N	Y	Y*

	8.1	Project website	Using data/material generated by project activities and consent to use personal data in line with GDPR (Name, email, country, company, occupation)	Project data and humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	Task	Activity	Type of data	Subject	Newly generated/ already existing data	Data format (Excel, Word, text file)	Nature of data (numerical, oral, visual)	Data type (observational, experimental, simulated/ modelled, derived from databases)	Data volume (if known 1 - 500 MB = small, 501 MB - 5 GB = medium, over 5 GB = large)	Methodology of data collection	Personal/ sensitive data? Yes/No	Will data be published? Yes/No	Metadata file done? Yes/No
WP8	8.1	Project newsletter	Using data/material generated by project activities and consent to use personal data in line with GDPR (Name, email, country, company, occupation)	Project data and humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	8.2	Knowledge products: policy toolkit	Using data/material generated by project activities. Policy toolkit embedded on project website which uses personal data when consented in line with GDPR (Name, email, country, company, occupation)	Project data and humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	8.2	Knowledge products: Open access repository, practice abstracts, motion design	Using data/material generated by project activities. Products embedded on project website which uses personal data when consented in line with GDPR (Name, email,	Project data and humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*

		journeys, videos	country, company, occupation)										
	8.3	Establishing Community of Practice (CoP) and regular communication with CoP	Personal details (name/organisation/occupation) of CoP members and their feedback	Project data and humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	Task	Activity	Type of data	Subject	Newly generated/ already existing data	Data format (Excel, Word, text file)	Nature of data (numerical, oral, visual)	Data type (observational, experimental, simulated/modelled, derived from databases)	Data volume (if known 1 - 500 MB = small, 501 MB - 5 GB = medium, over 5 GB = large)	Methodology of data collection	Personal/ sensitive data? Yes/No	Will data be published? Yes/No	Metadata file done? Yes/No
WP8	8.4	2 large conferences / share fairs	Using data/material generated by project activities in registration (name/organisation/occupation)	Humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	8.5	Early career programme	Personal details of participants and individual progress reports	Humans	New	Word	Text	Database	<10MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
WP9	9.1	Control of project progress and quality of deliverables	All data used and generated by project activities and contact details for Innovation Management Group	Project data, human data	New	Word file	Text	Database	<5 MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	9.2	Management of administrative data	All data used and generated by project activities	Project data incl. financial data	New	Word and Excel files	Text, numerical	Database	<5 MB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*
	9.3	Management of project data and Data Management Plan	All data used and generated by project activities	Project data	New	Word and Excel files	Text, numerical	Database	<30GB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	Y*

	9.4	Organisation of six consortium meetings	Details of all project participants, minutes and data arising from meetings	Humans	New	Word files	Text, oral, visual	Database	<1 GB	Word documents (offline)	Y	N	N
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WP10	10.1	Management of procedures and criteria for meeting human ethics requirements	Procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participant, templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets	Humans	New	Word files	Text	Database	<1MB	Word documents (offline)	N	N	Y*
	10.2	Data protection	Description of restrictions on data use / access	Humans	New	Word files	Text	Database	<1MB	Word documents (offline)	N	N	Y*
	10.3	Ethics requirements: animals	Details of animal experiments' adherence to the Three Rs principles	Animals	New	Word files	Text	Database	<1MB	Word documents (offline)	N	N	Y*